

SUPERIORITY COMPLEX AND POLICE BRUTALITY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Excessive use of force or high-handed or police brutality against suspects or bystanders has been a recurring decimal in Nigeria since the colony days. This research sought to investigate the influence of the superiority complex exhibited by Nigerian police officers as a cause for police brutality in Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for the study. One state per six geo-political zones was selected to ensure the effective gathering of data. Structured questionnaires with multiple options were distributed to respondents in six sampled states of one state per geo-political zone. A total of 5, 837 samples size derived from selected states from the six geo-political zones were adopted for the study. Data derived from the field survey were subjected to a chi-square test of the significant relationship between the study variables. The findings of the study show that police brutality stems from the psychological problems associated with a superiority complex which makes the Nigerian Police officers feel and demonstrate superiority to the Nigerian masses which they were employed to serve and protect. It was also found that the public reaction to police brutality is either through aggressive violent protest or regressive verbal condemnation. The study recommendations suggested some remedies such as psychological and criminal background checks of applicants and regular orientation programmes and conferences should be held for the Nigeria Police Force to educate them on their duty call to serve not to threaten the public.

Keywords: Superiority complex, police brutality, police, and Nigeria

Introduction

A police officer in Nigeria is an integral member of the Nigeria Police Force (NPF). He serves as the most visible armed representative of the government, engaging daily with the public to uphold governmental laws and regulations. Such interactions often lead to tensions and disagreements. In instances of conflict with the public, a police officer may stray from established protocols and exhibit a heavy-handed approach. While the public acknowledges the necessity and significance of police presence in society, they frequently criticize the

methods employed by law enforcement. These operational methods are often rooted in a self-perception of superiority, leading officers to expect unquestioned compliance with their orders. This mind-set frequently results in confrontations with the community (Ojukwu, 2011). This context has contributed to numerous instances of police brutality in Nigeria, including the infamous Apo six killings in 2005, which sparked the “#END SARS” protests by youth in 2022, as well as the killing of the Boko Haram founder in 2009.

The reputation of the police in Nigeria has been significantly tarnished. The police are aware of this issue and have implemented various public relations campaigns over the years, yet these efforts have proven ineffective. For instance, the slogan "Police is your friend" has failed to alter the public's negative perception of law enforcement. It is important to note that the excessive use of force, heavy-handedness, and brutality are not unique to Nigeria or Africa. A study conducted in the United States by Barker in 1986 found that among 45% of police stations surveyed, 40% of officers acknowledged having used excessive force against members of the public at times (Roberg *et al.*, 2012). The detrimental impact of this strained relationship between the police and the public is that it hampers the flow of intelligence information that could assist the police in their duties. Nevertheless, both the causes and consequences of this discord require thorough scientific investigation and validation. Based on this background, this research sought to examine the influence of superiority complex on police brutality inflicted upon the Nigerian polity by the force.

Statement of the Problem

Nigeria has experienced a democratic civilian administration since 1999, marking a span of 24 years as of 2023. In a democratic framework, adherence to constitutional provisions is typically expected, particularly regarding the rule of law and the rights of citizens. However, this does not seem to be the reality in Nigeria, where police operations continue to resemble those of a military dictatorship. The rights of citizens, as enshrined in Chapter 4 of the 1999 Constitution, are frequently disregarded and violated, particularly affecting the ordinary citizen. For instance, Section 4 of the Nigeria Police Code of Conduct, as outlined in the Nigeria Police Act of 2020, stipulates that "force shall be used only after discussion, negotiation, and persuasion be inappropriate or ineffective." While the use of force may sometimes be necessary, every police officer is expected to avoid unnecessary infliction of pain or suffering and to refrain from engaging in cruel, degrading, or inhuman treatment of any individual (Nigeria Police Act, 2020, p. 270). Likewise, the amended Constitution of Nigeria, 1999, in Section 34(1a) of Chapter 4, titled "Fundamental Rights," asserts that "no person shall be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading treatment." Thus, while there is no shortage of legal provisions against police brutality and torture, such acts continue to occur. Adejo in 1998 corroborated this troubling situation, stating, "I have heard of a police officer handcuffing a suspect and slapping him in the face in front of a group of people; I have also heard of police escorts of electoral materials looking the other way for fraudulent practices to be perpetrated."

The issue at hand involves instances where police officers have threatened the life of a suspect in their custody, expressing a desire for the suspect to attempt an escape so that they could "shoot him." Additionally, there are reports of police officers turning a blind eye to a victim being lynched, justifying their inaction by stating that they "are not on duty" (Adejo, 1998). The police acknowledge that such occurrences happen from time to time, attributing

them to "a few bad apples that tarnish the organization's reputation" (Jika, 1998). This research aimed to examine the influence of the superiority complex of the Nigeria Police Force on police brutality in Nigeria.

Research Objective

The main objective of this study was to examine how the superiority complex influences police brutality among the members of the Nigeria Police Force and the Nigerian masses.

Research Hypothesis

H₀: there is no significant relationship between the superiority complex and police brutality in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Causes of Police Brutality

Police brutality, characterized by the excessive use of force, can be attributed to various factors. Odinkalu (2004) posits that it is a legacy inherited from British colonial rule, which has been perpetuated and reinforced over time. He asserts that the police served as a blunt instrument for suppressing organized or popular dissent, operating under the authority of a European Inspector General. According to his analysis, the predominantly white police officers managed the institution with a culture of unyielding "Force," wherein the "natives" within the colonial police were denied the autonomy to engage with the local populations. These "native" officers were expected to follow orders from their European superiors and were conditioned to feel fortunate for their positions. Over time, the "native" police personnel began to emulate the behaviours and attitudes of their European counterparts. This dynamic has hindered the development of a culture conducive to peaceful, proactive, or constructive interaction with local communities. Furthermore, he contends that the military dictatorships that governed Nigeria from 1966 instilled a command mentality within the police, leading to a police-civil relationship characterized by a military-style language of "with immediate effect."

Certain authors attribute police brutality to the stress experienced by law enforcement officers. A study conducted in the United States by Loo (2005) indicates that this stress can arise from various aspects of police work, including excessive workloads, irregular shift patterns, exposure to violent and life-threatening scenarios, and the frustration associated with unresolved cases. Additionally, stress may stem from organizational factors such as departmental politics, insufficient resources and equipment, lack of support and recognition from management, and autocratic leadership styles. The criminal justice system also contributes to this stress through demands related to court appearances, challenges faced in legal proceedings, and the perception that the justice system is slow and overly lenient towards offenders. Furthermore, community factors play a role; when the public fails to appreciate the police's efforts, it can lead to a sense of apathy regarding support for law enforcement. Lastly, familial issues, including the impact of shift work, temporary assignments, and postings, can disrupt both family and social life, potentially affecting the physical and mental well-being of officers (as cited in Roberg *et al.*, 2012).

Similarly, in Nigeria, Davies (1998) argued that the police also suffer from work stress

or what he calls over – work leading to fatigue and nervousness while carrying arms thereby making them a danger to the public. Explaining further he said of all the state agencies responsible for security, law enforcement and protection of lives and properties the Nigeria police is the most visible, over worked, most stretched, most exposed and under paid.

Other authors like Ojukwu and Odinkalu think that it is as a result of superiority complex on the part of the police. According to Ojukwu;

“Given the traditional origin of the police as instruments of the powerful occupants of government circles, the tendency had been for the police officers to see themselves as superior to the people... the police officer...see himself as a “he who must be subjugated” (Ojukwu, 2011). Odinkalu also underscores this fact by opining that, :...with a culture of blunt and unquestioning force, “... this long history oppressive policing has made the police to be “unaccountable power” to the people” (Odinkalu, 2004).

Another way of determining the cause of police brutality is by assessing their work environment. How are their remuneration, training condition of service and equipment? Are they good and attractive? On the issue of work environment, Okonkwo is averse that several factors militate against police performance. He listed them as poor facilities, inadequate manpower, inadequate qualification and training, wrong orientation, very poor service conditions and poor police public relations. He cited a study carried out by the Nigerian Institute of Advance Legal Studies that showed that...out of 35 police stations investigated, 68.6% lacked adequate staff for the operation and 55.6% lacked adequate staff for administrative duties, as for stationery, the pictures were dismal. Of the 36 police stations covered only 2 that is 5.6% had stationery while 35 (94.45%) had none. Furniture, raincoats, and flashlights were completely inadequate about such other facilities as electric light points, fans, walkie-talkies, rifles, and batter charges, among others, 7 out of every 10 stations did not have them.” (Okonwo, 1998).

Aliyu (1998) similarly contends that the police force suffers from inadequate funding. He posits that for the police to enhance their efficiency, they require improved financial support and resources to effectively combat crime in Nigeria. Another commentator on the issue of police brutality is Osoba, who asserts that the police face not only a lack of proper tools and equipment but also insufficient salary structures and compensation. He notes that police officers, particularly those in lower ranks, experience job-related frustration, as evidenced by their worn-out uniforms, tattered boots, and substandard living conditions in overcrowded and poorly maintained barracks (Osoba, 1998). These perspectives from various authors shed light on the underlying causes of police brutality and will be instrumental in the analysis of this issue in Nigeria.

Nature of Police Brutality

Police brutality manifests in numerous forms. In their analysis, Roberg *et al.*, (2012) identified several examples prevalent in the United States, including physical assaults such as striking with a fist, the use of a horse whip, rubber hoses, clubs, and whips, as well as hitting individuals with rifle butts. Other methods cited include waterboarding, where a person's head is submerged in water, the application of electric shocks, dragging individuals by their hair, twisting limbs, burning with lit cigars, dousing with cold water from a hose, forced water intake through the nose, exposure to tear gas in confined spaces, fatal choking, and beatings with police batons, among others. The authors noted that while such incidents were common in the 1930s, there has been a significant improvement in the situation in contemporary times.

In Nigeria, police brutality manifests in various forms, including the use of machete blades to beat arrested suspects in an attempt to extract confessions; slapping and kicking suspects during their arrest; whipping bystanders with horse whips; firing live ammunition into peaceful protests; administering electric shocks to suspects; detaining individuals without charges or prosecution; forcibly seizing and inspecting the mobile phones of citizens; deploying tear gas and assaulting innocent bystanders under the pretext of their proximity to alleged crime scenes; and profiling young individuals, leading to arrests based solely on their attire or hairstyle, often under the suspicion of being involved in internet fraud.

Three notable instances of police brutality that have incited violence in Nigeria include the Apo six killings in Abuja in 2005, which triggered public riots; the police killing of Mohammed Yusuf, the founder of Boko Haram, in Maiduguri in July 2009, which catalyzed Boko Haram terrorism in Northern Nigeria; and the ongoing killings and abuse of innocent citizens by the Special Anti-Robbery Squad (SARS) in 2021, which ignited nationwide protests under the banner “#END SARS,” resulting in the destruction of government properties, private businesses, and the loss of innocent lives.

Theoretical Framework

Emile Durkheim's Theory of Policing

Jackson and Sunshine (2007) currently used a neo-Durkheimian attitude in the look at public self-belief of the police. According to Jackson and Sunshine, Durkheim proposed that society judges the police following their ability to defend and represent the morals and values of society. Jackson and Sunshine (2007) based on Durkheim's theory of policing posits that people judge whether the police are representatives of community values and morals. According to scholars, people judged a range of things in their community as hostile to social order, and by linking such symbols of breakdown with the danger of victimisation by the police.

The application of the theory to the study is in the fact that the study area is that; the police as an institution, as a representative of the safety to the people is expected to uphold the moral boundaries of the community and protect lives and properties, while seeking to arrest and work on prosecuting those considered to be deviants or criminals by the community. But the police has turned to become a threat to the people due to their commanding maltreatment of the masses which is driven by the superiority complex of the police officers to the masses.

Methodology

Survey research methodology was adopted for this study. This method is adopted when a researcher uses fieldwork to collect data from a wide geographical area and a large population (Mboho, 2010). The study had as its scope the entire country. To ensure the representation of the entire country, geo-political zones were used in the distribution of the instrument. In each zone, one state was randomly selected as follows:

North–Central (Benue State), North–East (Borno State), North–West (Sokoto State), South–East (Anambra State), South–South (Akwa Ibom State) and South–West (Lagos State).

Ball and Gall (in Bereenu – Nnabugwu, 2006:11) advocate that for a population of up to 1000, 5000, and 10000 it should be pegged at 20%, 10% and 5% respectively. Therefore

leveraging on Ball and Gall's recommendations stated above, which show that the larger the study population the less the percentage of sample size, we hereby choose point zero two per cent (0.02%) of the study population of the 6 sample states as sample size which is 5,837 as shown in Table 1 below;

Table 1 Sample size per state

S/No	Geo-Political Zone	States	National population (2006 Population Census)	Study Population (Proportion of National Population)	Sample Size per state
1	North – Central	Benue	4,219,244	14.5	846
2	North – East	Borno	4,151,193	14.2	829
3	North – West	Sokoto	3,696,999	12.7	741
4	South – East	Anambra	4,182,032	14.3	835
5	South South	Akwa Ibom	3,920,208	13.4	782
6	South West	Lagos	9,013,354	30.9	1,804
		Total	291,830,030	100%	5,837

Source: compiled by the Authors

Table 1 shows that out of the 2006 population Census total figures of 291,830,030 for the six sample states, 5,837 being 0.02% of this total Census population was arrived at as sample size for the research work.

The data collection method involved administering a series of questions pertinent to the subject of this research, utilizing a four-point Likert scale comprising Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). This approach was detailed in Section B of the Questionnaire. The response option reflecting the most favorable opinion was allocated 4 points, while the least favorable option received 1 point. In the data analysis phase, the responses from participants were aggregated. The respective weights of 4, 3, 2, and 1 were applied to calculate the weighted frequencies for the categories of strongly agree, agree, disagree, and strongly disagree. Subsequently, percentage frequencies were computed to facilitate decision-making. A pertinent question arises: can significant differences exist among the frequencies of these items? To address this inquiry, a chi-square (X²) test statistic was utilized. The chi-square (X²) test was deemed appropriate as it assesses whether the entire range of values exhibits significant differences and allows for the identification of specific classes that contribute most to these differences by examining the chi-square (X²) value for each cell (Cole and King, 1970).

Findings

Hypothesis of the Study

H₀: there is no significant relationship between the superiority complex and police brutality in Nigeria.

To test this hypothesis, two groups of variables were identified as follows:

1. Superiority complex as independent variable.
2. Police brutality as the dependent variable

Chi – square (X^2) was used to analyse the data derived from a valid questionnaire received from 5,695 respondents in six states of the six geo-political zones of Nigeria.

The formula for chi-square is stated below:

$$\sum \frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$$

Where O = the Observed value distribution
 E = the expected value distribution
 \sum = summation of all items

Table 2. Chi-square Analysis of the Association between psychological problems such as work stress and superiority complex and police brutality.

S/No.	O	E	O - E	$\sum (O - E)^2$	$\frac{\sum (O - E)^2}{E}$
1	42	12	30	900	75
2	28.8	12	16.8	282.24	23.52
3	19.8	12	7.8	60.84	5.07
4	9.4	12	-2.6	6.76	0.56
Total					104.15

Source: computed by the authors

As shown in Table.2 above Chi-square = 104.15

Degree of freedom (df) = (n – 1)
 = 4 – 1
 = 3

Level of significance = 0.05

Critical (or Theoretical) $X^2 = 7.81$ (from Chi-square Distribution Table)

Table 2 above shows that the Chi-square value of 104.15 is larger than the critical X^2 value of 7.81 at a 0.05 level of significance. This means that the difference in the categories is real and significant. Accordingly, we uphold the hypothesis which states that “psychological problems of a police officer such as superiority complex tend to impact significantly on police brutality.”

Discussion of Findings

The results of the data analysis in table 2 above are significant because the Observed X^2 value of 104.15 is larger than the critical X^2 value of 7.81 at 0.05 level of significance with 3 as the degree of freedom. This result confirms the assertion that there is relationship between psychological problems such as work stress and superiority complex and police brutality. This result is in agreement with the findings of Davies (1998) and Ojukwu (2011). According to Davies the police also suffer from work stress and “over-work” leading to fatigue and nervousness while carrying arms thereby making such a policeman to be a danger to the public. Similarly, Ojukwu confirms that police officers see themselves as superior to the people, their (police's) orders must be obeyed and the people must obey and the people must be subjected.

Loo (2005) argues that police stress may come from work overload, shift work, exposure to violent and life – threatening situations, departmental politics, inadequate resources, lack of support and recognition from management, non – appreciation of police's efforts by the public among others.

Conclusion

The pronounced superiority complex exhibited by the Nigeria Police Force significantly contributes to instances of police brutality, which constitutes a violation of human rights. The persistent occurrence of such behaviour in Nigeria is concerning and has garnered the attention of vigilant citizens, as evidenced by the EndSARS protests in 2020. Research has identified several underlying causes of police brutality, including inadequate training, socioeconomic conditions, political influences, and psychological factors. Regardless of any rationalizations provided for police misconduct, this study has demonstrated that the daily operations of the police reveal a troubling pattern of rights violations and the detrimental impact of such brutality on victims. The repercussions of police brutality are both socio-economic and psychological, affecting the overall safety of the populace. This raises a critical question: are the police intended to safeguard or endanger the citizens? Consequently, this study has examined the government's initiatives aimed at addressing this issue and concluded that, despite the government's articulation of necessary actions to curb police brutality, the majority of these proposals remain unimplemented.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the study recommended that;

1. There should be psychological and criminal background checks of applicants during police recruitment exercise.
2. The government should conduct regular orientation programmes and conferences for the Nigeria Police Force to educate them on their duty call to serve not to threaten the public.

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